

HIVEMIND NEWSLETTER_03

From foundations to implementation

General Assembly in Berlin

In January, the HIVEMIND consortium gathered in Berlin for its General Assembly, hosted by Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz, to review progress and prepare for the next stage of development.

A major milestone was the completion of WP1, consolidating project requirements, KPIs and architectural decisions into a shared framework. Partners also refined a common understanding of agents within HIVEMIND, discussing their responsibilities, interactions and role across the software development lifecycle.

With these foundations in place, attention turned to implementation, integration and deployment. The meeting also advanced plans for dissemination, exploitation and collaboration with related European initiatives.

How it was

Joining forces across Europe

Alliance for Generative Software Engineering

HIVEMIND has joined [AI4SWEng](#), [MOSAICO](#) and [ASTIR](#) in establishing the Alliance for Generative Software Engineering. The initiative brings together projects working at the intersection of artificial intelligence and software engineering with the shared objective of accelerating the trustworthy adoption of Generative AI in software development.

Through joint activities, coordinated outreach and shared engagement with stakeholders, the alliance aims to strengthen links between research, industry and real-world deployment. Ultimately, the projects will deliver interoperability-driven building blocks to enable scalability and drive a structured transformation of software engineering practices beyond code generation.

Focusing on who will use the results

Mid-term Exploitation and IPR Workshop

On 24 March, partners came together for HIVEMIND's mid-term Exploitation and IPR Workshop, led by María Ignacia Culell (AUSTRALO). The discussions centred on a simple question: who will use what we are building? Partners reviewed the project's key exploitable results, identified potential users and early adopters, and explored pathways to support uptake beyond the project's lifetime.

The workshop also examined business opportunities, ownership considerations and routes towards sustainable deployment. Additionally, the session focused on the categorization of these results and defined the pathways for both the individual and joint exploitation objectives of our

partners. This work helps ensure that Hivemind technologies remain aligned with real operational needs as development progresses.

HIVEMIND on the international stage

Research contributions across Europe

Over the past months, Hivemind partners have presented project-related work at conferences, workshops and research forums across Europe.

- Behrooz Sangchoolie of RISE Research Institutes of Sweden contributed to discussions on dependable and secure computing at events hosted by Universidade de Coimbra and the IFIP Working Group 10.4 Workshop in Riga, presenting perspectives linked to Hivemind's work on software quality and testing agents.
- Xavier Franch of Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya participated in ICSE 2026, CAIN 2026 and WSESE 2026, sharing research on emerging software engineering practices and the growing role of Generative AI in the field.
- At the Generative AI in Software Engineering Summer School 2026 in Tampere, Razieh Akbari of Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya presented ongoing work on TaskGenAgent, a research initiative within Hivemind exploring how Generative AI can support Agile development management and task coordination.
- At ACİLTEK 2026 in İzmir, İdil Gökalp Köse of HAVELSAN presented Hivemind's disaster management use case, demonstrating how multi-agent systems can support emergency response and crisis coordination.
- At the Language Resources and Evaluation Conference 2026 in Palma de Mallorca, Fabio Barth of DFKI introduced two resources developed within the project: PolyglotQL, a multilingual Text-to-SPARQL dataset generation pipeline, and SciLaD, a large-scale dataset for scientific language processing. Both support transparent and reproducible AI development.

New publications

Supporting Open Science

Recent work from the HIVEMIND community explores the role of AI in software testing, scientific language processing and multilingual knowledge representation.

AI-Powered Software Testing Tools: Full Autonomy Remains a Distant Goal

Based on a review of 56 commercial AI-assisted testing tools, this study examines where AI can support software testing and where human expertise remains indispensable. The findings suggest that, despite rapid progress, fully autonomous software testing remains some distance away.

SciLaD: A Large-Scale, Transparent, Reproducible Dataset for Natural Scientific Language Processing

Built from publicly available scientific publications and open-source tools, SciLaD provides a large-scale resource for scientific language processing. Alongside the dataset, the authors released the complete generation pipeline, supporting transparency and reproducibility in future research.

PolyglotQL: A Pipeline for Multilingual Text-to-SPARQL Dataset Generation

PolyglotQL introduces an open framework for creating multilingual Text-to-SPARQL datasets and evaluating semantic parsing models. The work demonstrates how structured contextual information can improve performance across languages and knowledge domains.

All publications are available through the HIVEMIND website.

[Access the publications](#)

Thank you for following our progress. We'll continue to keep you informed on the next steps and achievements as HIVEMIND moves forward. For more details, visit our [website](#).

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101189745. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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